

Carolina Senn

Address: University of Bern,
Institute of Plant Sciences,
Paleoecology,
Altenbergrain 21,
3013 Bern, Switzerland

mail: carolina.senn@ips.unibe.ch

phone: +41 31 631 49 22

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-8775-7190

Dr. Erika Gobet

Address: University of Bern,
Institute of Plant Sciences,
Paleoecology,
Altenbergrain 21,
3013 Bern, Switzerland

mail: erika.gobet@ips.unibe.ch

phone: +41 31 631 49 31

ORCID ID: -

Prof. Dr. Willy Tinner

Address: University of Bern,
Institute of Plant Sciences,
Paleoecology,
Altenbergrain 21,
3013 Bern, Switzerland

mail: willy.tinner@ips.unibe.ch

phone: +41 31 631 49 32

ORCID ID: 0000-0001-7352-0144

Dr. Jacqueline FN van Leeuwen

Address: University of Bern,
Institute of Plant Sciences,
Paleoecology,
Altenbergrain 21,
3013 Bern, Switzerland

mail: jacqueline.vanleeuwen@ips.unibe.ch

phone: -

ORCID ID: -

Dr. Vivian A Felde

Address: University of Bergen
Department of Biological Sciences
Thormøhlensgate 53A
N-5006 Bergen, Norway

mail: vivian.Felde@uib.no

phone: +47 55 58 81 27

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-2855-0894

Dr. César Morales-Molino

Address: University of Bern,
Institute of Plant Sciences,
Paleoecology,
Altenbergrain 21,
3013 Bern, Switzerland

mail: cesar.morales@ips.unibe.ch

phone: +41 31 631 49 85

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9464-862X

2 **Modern pollen – vegetation – plant diversity relationships** 3 **across large environmental gradients in northern Greece**

4 **Authors:** Carolina Senn¹, Willy Tinner¹, Vivian A Felde², Erika Gobet¹,
5 Jacqueline FN van Leeuwen¹, César Morales-Molino¹

6 **Affiliations:** ¹Institute of Plant Sciences and Oeschger Centre for Climate
7 Change Research, University of Bern, Switzerland

8 ²Department of Biological Sciences and Bjerknes Centre for Climate Research,
9 University of Bergen, Norway

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11 **Abstract**

12 Past vegetation and biodiversity dynamics, reconstructed using
13 palaeoecological methods, can contribute to assessing the magnitude of the
14 current biodiversity crisis and anticipating future risks and challenges. Among
15 the different palaeoecological techniques, pollen analysis is probably the most
16 widely used to reconstruct vegetation and plant diversity changes through time.
17 Such reconstructions demand robust and comprehensive calibration studies
18 addressing the pollen representation of extant vegetation to be sound. However,
19 calibration studies are rare in the Mediterranean biodiversity hotspot,
20 particularly regarding plant diversity. Here, we contribute to filling this gap by
21 investigating the modern pollen signature of Mediterranean vegetation across a
22 large environmental gradient in northern Greece. At each sampling site (n=61),
23 we quantitatively compared the composition and diversity of plant (vegetation
24 surveys) and pollen assemblages (moss/topsoil samples) using numerical

25 techniques. Further, we compared these terrestrial pollen assemblages with
26 those from lake sediment surface samples of the same region. We found an
27 overall good match between plant and pollen assemblages, with maquis and
28 mixed deciduous forest displaying particularly distinct pollen signatures. In
29 contrast, the high regional importance of pines and oaks and their large pollen
30 production blurred the pollen representation of other forested vegetation types
31 and of shrublands and grasslands. Plant and pollen richness and their evenness
32 showed similar declining trends with increasing altitude, but plant and pollen
33 evenness bore a better match than richness. A more detailed vegetation-specific
34 view on the data suggests that pine pollen seriously affected pollen richness
35 and evenness in most of the pine-dominated stands. Lastly, our results suggest
36 a rather straightforward application of vegetation-pollen relationships from
37 moss/topsoil samples to interpret pollen assemblages from lakes in
38 Mediterranean settings.

39

40 **Keywords:** Surface samples, Mediterranean region, palaeoecology,
41 Multivariate Classification Tree, Indicator species, evenness, palynological
42 richness, pollen analysis

43 **1. Introduction**

44 The ongoing global climate change crisis is posing serious challenges to
45 biodiversity conservation and management (Dawson et al. 2011; Urban et al., 2016).
46 In this context, global biodiversity hotspots such as the Mediterranean Basin (*c.*
47 25,000 plant species, almost half of them endemic) are of particular importance
48 (Blondel et al., 2010; Myers et al., 2000; IPBES, 2018). Located in the northeastern

49 Mediterranean sub-region, Greece hosts one of the richest floras in the Mediterranean
50 Basin (c. 5,800 plant species), with a high proportion of narrow endemic species
51 (15.6%; Georghiou and Delipetrou, 2010). Because in Greece all major vegetation
52 types of the Mediterranean are represented, it offers a unique setting to investigate
53 southern European plant and vegetation diversity. The notably large number of plant
54 species mainly results from the following factors: i) located in Europe, Greece's
55 proximity to two other continents (Asia and Africa) makes it a biogeographical
56 crossroads; ii) Greece shows a high topographic diversity; iii) most of Greece
57 remained ice-free during the cold periods of the Quaternary (glaciations) and was
58 therefore a refugium for many European plant species; and iv) Greece has a very long
59 (> 8,000 years) history of human impact (e.g. Glais et al., 2016; Gassner et al., 2020).
60 Past natural environmental variability and human impacts have thus played a central
61 role in defining today's species diversity and distribution, as well as vegetation
62 composition and structure (Birks, 2012; Bottema, 1974; Georghiou and Delipetrou,
63 2010; Jahns, 2005; Tzedakis, 1993). Therefore, a deeper knowledge of past vegetation
64 and plant diversity, including natural biodiversity conditions prior to the establishment
65 of land use, is needed to better understand and manage present and future dynamics
66 (Willis et al., 2010).

67 Palaeoecology may provide such long-term perspectives on the dynamics of
68 vegetation and plant diversity, enabling us to reconstruct changes in the past
69 distribution of species and communities (e.g. Giesecke et al., 2017; Herring et al.,
70 2018; Morales-Molino et al., 2020a). Moreover, palaeoecology allows assessing the
71 roles of the different drivers of vegetation change, such as climate change or human
72 activities (e.g. Henne et al., 2013; Morales-Molino et al., 2020a). In this context, a
73 question that might be addressed by palaeoecology would be the origin of current
74 diversity: is it natural or has it been impacted by land use (e.g. Birks, 2012)? In

75 palaeoecology, pollen analysis is a widely used tool to reconstruct vegetation history
76 and to analyse temporal shifts in plant diversity (e.g. Birks and Line, 1992; Felde et
77 al., 2018; Giesecke et al., 2019). However, the interpretation of fossil pollen
78 assemblages is not straightforward given that differences in production, dispersal, and
79 preservation distort the linkages between plant and pollen abundances (e.g. Felde et
80 al., 2014b). To overcome this issue, numerous studies have investigated the
81 relationship between modern vegetation and its pollen representation all over the
82 world (e.g. Felde et al., 2014b; Ge et al., 2017; Hagemans et al., 2019; Henga-
83 Botsikabobe et al., 2020). More recently, some studies have focused on improving
84 reconstructions of past plant diversity and ultimately assisting conservation strategies
85 by calibrating the modern pollen-plant diversity relationships in surface samples (e.g.
86 Felde et al., 2016; Goring et al., 2013; Gosling et al., 2018; Jantz et al., 2014; Matthias
87 et al., 2015; Meltsov et al., 2013; Reitalu et al., 2019). Although modern pollen
88 representation has also been widely investigated throughout the Mediterranean region
89 (e.g. Fall, 2012; Gerasimidis et al., 2006; Glais et al., 2016; López-Sáez et al., 2015,
90 2018, 2019; Morales-Molino et al., 2020b), studies dealing specifically with plant-
91 pollen diversity relationships are very rare (Connor et al., 2021; Papadopoulou et al.,
92 2021). Additionally, a notable proportion of these Mediterranean studies does not
93 cover large ecological gradients, as they have relatively narrow geographical scopes or
94 focus on specific plant communities. Studies addressing the modern pollen
95 representation of Mediterranean vegetation along large territories and environmental
96 gradients are thus still needed, and in this context the southern Balkan Peninsula with
97 its extremely diverse vegetation (from thermomediterranean maquis to alpine
98 meadows and scree) represents an ideal setting to conduct such research.

99 Pollen-vegetation calibration studies usually rely on the analysis of moss
100 polster, topsoil and lake sediment samples. Moss polster pollen assemblages are

101 generally well-suited to interpret pollen assemblages from peat sequences from mires
102 or bogs, while lake surface samples are preferred as guidance for the interpretation of
103 lake sediment records (Poska, 2013; Bradley, 2015). Although differences in the
104 pollen source areas of lakes and mires have long been acknowledged (e.g. Jacobson
105 and Bradshaw, 1981; Poska, 2013; Sugita, 1994), studies comparing moss polster and
106 lake sediment surface samples are rare and mostly concern temperate and boreal
107 vegetation (Lisitsyna et al., 2012; Pardoe et al., 2010; Wilmshurst and McGlone,
108 2005).

109 In this study, we aim at filling these gaps by examining the relationship
110 between vegetation and pollen assemblages along a wide environmental gradient in
111 northern Greece, spanning from coastal maquis to subalpine meadows, with a
112 particular focus on diversity. We conducted vegetation surveys at 61 sampling sites
113 corresponding to eight major vegetation types and collected moss/topsoil samples
114 ('terrestrial surface samples' hereafter) to analyse the modern pollen representation.
115 Additionally, we retrieved lake surface sediment samples ('lake surface samples'
116 hereafter) from 12 sites located in the same region to compare and link their pollen
117 assemblages with the terrestrial surface samples. Later, we analysed the plant and
118 pollen datasets using detrended correspondence analysis, Procrustes analysis,
119 multivariate classification trees, and correlation analysis to assess quantitatively the
120 linkages between pollen assemblages and vegetation composition as well as between
121 pollen and plant diversity. More specifically, we aimed at: (i) assessing to what extent
122 pollen assemblages co-vary with plant assemblages and vegetation types and which
123 might be the potential drivers; (ii) evaluating whether the pollen composition of
124 terrestrial surface samples is comparable with that of lake surface samples; and, (iii)
125 investigating whether pollen diversity reflects accurately plant diversity.

126 **2. Material and Methods**

127 **2.1 Sampling, vegetation surveys, and pollen analyses**

128 Our 61 sampling sites are spread across northern Greece, spanning an
129 elevational gradient from 0 to 2449 m a.s.l, and covering most of the regional
130 vegetation zones of Greece (Figure 1, Supplementary Table 1). We grouped the sites
131 into eight different vegetation types defined according to the composition and
132 structure of the extant local and extra-local vegetation (e.g. coastal mesomediterranean
133 maquis, temperate and subalpine forests, alpine treeless vegetation). We denominated
134 the forest vegetation types following the European forest types (Barbati et al., 2007)
135 and the “Map of the Natural Vegetation of Europe” (Bohn and Neuhäuslová,
136 2000/2003) (summarised in Supplementary Figure 1).

137 [insert Figure 1.]

138 At each site, we recorded vegetation composition within a plot of *c.* 10x10 m
139 with a focus on woody species (trees and shrubs), in April (lowlands) and July 2019
140 (uplands). Specifically, we recorded plant species (presence/absence) and canopy
141 cover (presence/absence) every metre along two orthogonal 10-m long transects (2x10
142 points). We later transformed the records of both variables into a semi-quantitative
143 scale as follows: presence in 0, 1, 2..., to 20 out of 20 points equals to a ground cover
144 of 0, 5, 10..., 100%. For herbs and ferns, we only recorded the presence or absence in
145 the plots.

146 We identified plant species using regional floras (Dimopoulos et al., 2016;
147 Lafranchis and Sfikas, 2009; Pignatti, 1982; Strid, 1980). Due to the phenological
148 status, we could identify some plant taxa only to genus or even family level (e.g. *Rosa*,
149 *Lactuca*, Poaceae, Cyperaceae), but we numbered different taxa within a family or
150 genus to keep track of diversity (e.g. Apiaceae 1, Apiaceae 2). The sampling season

151 and its associated phenological status also hampered detection and identification of
152 some plant species: for instance, late-season and early-season herbs went undetected in
153 April and July respectively and distinguishing *Ostrya carpinifolia* from *Carpinus*
154 *orientalis* was challenging in early spring.

155 In the same plots, we collected terrestrial surface samples (mainly moss
156 polsters, but also O and A soil horizons) in several spots distributed all over the plot.
157 Once in the laboratory, we homogenized the sample and treated 1 cm³ for pollen
158 analysis following a slightly modified protocol with respect to Moore et al. (1991): we
159 skipped the first HCl step and applied HF only to samples containing soil. We
160 identified and counted pollen and spore types at 400×, 630×, and 1000×
161 magnifications aided by the reference collection at the Institute of Plant Sciences of
162 the University of Bern, dichotomic keys, and photo atlases (Beug, 2004; Moore et al.,
163 1991; Punt, 1976-2009; Reille, 1992). A minimum sum of 500 pollen grains was
164 generally achieved, although bad pollen preservation prevented us from reaching this
165 number in some samples (minimum 437). We harmonized pollen type taxonomy
166 according to the European Pollen Database (EPD, Giesecke et al., 2019). We split
167 *Quercus* pollen into three groups according to morphological features (Beug, 2004): 1)
168 *Quercus pubescens* type, which includes all the *Quercus* section *Quercus* species of
169 the region (e.g. *Quercus frainetto*, *Q. petraea*, *Q. pubescens*, *Q. robur*), 2) *Quercus*
170 *ilex* type, which includes the *Quercus* section *Ilex* species, i.e. *Quercus ilex* and
171 *Quercus coccifera*, and 3) *Quercus cerris* type, which includes the *Quercus* section
172 *Cerris* species (e.g. *Quercus cerris* and *Quercus trojana*; Denk et al., 2017). *Ostrya*
173 type includes also pollen of *Carpinus orientalis* and *Juniperus* type might include
174 pollen from other Cupressaceae (Beug, 2004). We plotted pollen diagrams using Tilia
175 (Version 2.6.1) (Grimm, 1992-2019).

176 To assess the relationship between the pollen assemblages from terrestrial and
177 lake surface samples we retrieved short cores from the following twelve lakes (Figure
178 1; Supplementary Table 2) using UWITEC or Kajak gravity corers: Limni Kastoria
179 (KAS), Limni Petres (PET), Limni Vegoritisi (VEG), Limni Zazari (ZAZ) – cored in
180 2016 –, Limni Amvrakia (AMV), Limni Dojran (DOJ), Limni Ioannina (IOA), Limni
181 Koroneia (KOR), Limni Megali Prespa (PRE), Drakolimni Smolika (SMO), Limni
182 Strofilia (STRO), and Limni Volvi (VOL) – cored in 2020 – (Supplementary Dataset
183 7). We treated 1 to 2 cm³ of the uppermost sediment following the standard procedure
184 in Moore et al. (1991), and the pollen was analysed as described above for terrestrial
185 samples. We re-counted the surface sample from Limni Zazari (Gassner et al., 2020)
186 to avoid biases in the pollen diversity related to differences in the taxonomic precision
187 achieved by different analysts.

188

189 **2.2 Pollen and plant data processing and environmental variables**

190 For the numerical analyses we considered two data sets: 1) terrestrial plant
191 species abundances (estimated ground cover, %); and 2) pollen relative abundances
192 (%). Pollen percentages were calculated with respect to the terrestrial pollen sum
193 excluding pollen of aquatic and wetland plants and spores in lake surface samples. In
194 contrast, all pollen taxa found in the terrestrial samples were considered non-aquatic as
195 they come from terrestrial sites. The percentage data were Hellinger-transformed
196 because it is recommended for species abundance data with many zero presences (as
197 in our case) and to preserve Euclidean distance for the analysis in Cartesian space
198 (Legendre and Birks, 2012b). For further diversity analyses, we compiled available
199 information about the growing form (tree, shrub, herb, fern) and pollination mode

200 (wind-pollinated vs. not wind-pollinated) of the plant species and pollen types
201 (Landolt et al., 2010; Pignatti, 1982).

202 We tested the relationships between the pollen and plant datasets with the
203 environmental variables elevation, canopy cover, and distance to the sea. These three
204 variables were selected because of their relevance from an ecological and pollen
205 dispersal perspective (elevation is related to temperature and precipitation; distance to
206 the sea is a proxy for continentality; canopy cover may have an influence on pollen
207 transport) and to avoid collinearity with other environmental variables (e.g. distance to
208 the sea was correlated with latitude). The environmental data for each sampling site
209 were obtained as follows: elevation (Knapp and Verdin, 1998; processed in ArcGIS),
210 canopy cover (fieldwork; see above), and distance to the sea (“rnatuarearth” – South
211 2017 – and “rgdal” – Bivand et al., 2019 – packages running in R version 3.6.5 – R
212 Core Team, 2020).

213

214 **2.3 Correspondence between plant and pollen assemblages**

215 We used Detrended Correspondence Analysis (DCA) to estimate species
216 turnover in standard deviation (SD) units. Considering the length of the DCA axis 1 of
217 the plant dataset (9.66 SD), we decided to use the DCA as it is a unimodal-based
218 ordination method (Birks et al., 2012). We conducted DCA on the plant and pollen
219 assemblage data sets and added the environmental variables passively to the
220 ordinations because this prevents them from affecting the results directly. We used
221 Procrustes analysis to compare the plant and pollen DCA axes scores and thereby
222 quantify the similarities between paired assemblages from the same site, whereby the
223 rotation was non-symmetric on the favour of the plant data sets. A Procrustes sum-of-
224 squares m^2 of 0 (a number between 0 and 1) indicates that the ordinations are identical

225 (Felde et al., 2014b; Goodall, 1991; Gower, 1975; Jackson, 1995; Peres-Neto and
226 Jackson, 2001). Further, lake surface samples were added as supplementary data to the
227 pollen DCA ordination plot to evaluate the comparability between the pollen
228 composition from the terrestrial and lake surface samples.

229 Multivariate classification trees (MCT) were used to investigate how well the
230 plant and pollen assemblages can distinguish our eight vegetation types (De'ath, 2002;
231 Ouellette and Legendre, 2013; Simpson and Birks, 2012; Therneau et al., 2014). Tree
232 size was based on the 1-SE rule of Breiman et al. (1984). We also identified the
233 discriminant species (i.e. those taxa contributing most to the splitting into two
234 branches) and indicator species (i.e. those taxa best defining a vegetation type) using
235 an Indicator Value (IndVal) threshold of 20% and $p < 0.05$ with the MVPARTwrap
236 extension of the 'mvpart' R package (Borcard et al., 2018; Legendre and Legendre,
237 2012). Moreover, MCT analysis allows calculation of: (i) the overall explained
238 variation of the dataset (adjusted R^2), and (ii) the accuracy of vegetation type
239 prediction at a given sampling site based on the corresponding plant or pollen
240 assemblage (Felde et al., 2014a, b; Gordon, 1999; Hubert and Arabie, 1985; Legendre
241 and Birks, 2012a).

242 **2.4 Diversity analyses**

243 We conducted diversity analyses on the entire plant and pollen assemblage
244 datasets, on the subset of trees and shrubs, and the subset of wind-pollinated trees and
245 shrubs. We focused on woody species because their presence/absence was recorded
246 consistently (see section 2.1). This procedure also intends to minimise the dominance
247 of wind-pollinated taxa. We removed site number 54 from the two subsets because the
248 absence of woody species in the plot resulted in unsolvable diversity indices. We
249 calculated diversity indices on the percentage data of plant species and on the rarefied

250 pollen counts to reduce the effect of different counting effort (Birks and Line, 1992;
251 Chao et al., 2014). We used Hill numbers (N0, N1, N2; pollen's N0 is equal to pollen
252 richness [PRI]) and associated evenness ratios (E0, mod E0, E1, modE1, E3; see Felde
253 et al., 2016), as well as the Probability of Interspecific Encounter (PIE; Hurlbert,
254 1971) as a rough proxy for evenness.

255 Minimum pollen sums for the entire dataset, its subset of trees and shrubs, and
256 the subset of pollination mode were 437, 164, and 130, respectively. For the
257 rarefaction, the function *rrarefy()* of the R package “vegan” was used (Oksanen et al.,
258 2019). We did not rarefy the plant datasets, as proposed by Connor et al. (2021),
259 because of their semi-quantitative structure. In a second step, palynological richness
260 (PRI) was detrended (DE-PRI) with PIE to reduce the influence of high pollen
261 producers and dispersers (Colombaroli and Tinner, 2013) and to investigate if DE-PRI
262 is affected by evenness distortions.

263 Pearson's correlation matrices were calculated for the contrast between the
264 different indices of plant and pollen of the entire data, and the two subsets (Harrell Jr,
265 2020). Finally, N0, PRI, DE-PRI, and PIE were plotted against their sampling sites
266 clustered in vegetation groups, which are ordered along their median elevation, to
267 visually assess patterns (Wickham, 2016).

268 **3. Results and Interpretation**

269 **3.1 Pollen data**

270 We found 341 plant species and 133 pollen types (after taxonomic
271 harmonization). Pollen assemblages from mixed deciduous forests are mainly
272 dominated by pollen of deciduous trees (*Tilia*, *Castanea sativa*, *Alnus glutinosa* t. (t. =
273 type), *Platanus*, *Fraxinus ornus*), *Hedera helix*, and *Solanum dulcamara*, which only
274 occurs here (Figure 2). *Quercus pubescens* t. pollen dominates in samples from mixed

275 oak woodlands, mostly admixed with pollen of temperate deciduous trees and
276 *Juniperus* t. Non-arboreal pollen (NAP) is slightly more abundant. Beech-dominated
277 stands show a dominance of *Pinus sylvestris* t. pollen accompanied by *Fagus* and
278 some *Q. pubescens* t. *Pinus sylvestris* t. is also dominant in pine-dominated stands and
279 mixed fir forests, whereas in the latter, *Abies* and *Q. ilex* t. are more abundant. The
280 exceptionally high percentages of *Juniperus* t. pollen (49 %) found in site 58 (pine-
281 dominated stand) are remarkable. Compared to the following three vegetation types,
282 all these samples show high percentages of arboreal pollen (AP).

283 Pollen of evergreen mediterranean shrubs (e.g. *Erica*, *Phillyrea*, *Pistacia*,
284 *Cistus*, *Q. ilex* t.) dominate the maquis pollen assemblages (Figure 2). Shrublands have
285 more *Juniperus* t., *Q. pubescens* t., and *Ostrya* t. with higher percentages of NAP
286 (Figure 2). Grasslands have the highest percentages of NAP, mainly Poaceae and
287 *Artemisia* (Figure 3). Overall, pollen assemblages from mixed deciduous forests,
288 mixed oak woodlands, maquis, shrublands and grasslands are distinct and agree
289 reasonably well with their vegetation types (as described in Supplementary Figure 1).
290 On the contrary, the high abundance of *P. sylvestris* t. pollen makes pollen
291 assemblages from the temperate forests notably resemble each other. The exceptional
292 site number 58, however, records likely the many juniper shrubs found in the
293 understory.

294 [insert Figure 2, 3.]

295 **3.2 Correspondence and dissimilarities between plant and pollen assemblages**

296 DCA axis 1 for plant assemblages is notably longer than that of the pollen
297 dataset (9.657 SD vs. 2.109 SD respectively; Supplementary Figure 2). The large
298 turnover observed in plant assemblages reflects large differences in the plant
299 communities sampled, which is in turn related to the high number of plant species

300 identified. This diversity results from the large environmental gradients covered by our
301 sampling sites (*c.* 2500 m difference in altitude; 1 to 110 km distance to the sea). The
302 turnover in the pollen assemblages (Supplementary Figure 2d-f) is still relatively high
303 (see Felde et al., 2014a; Giesecke et al., 2019), certainly because of the same reason.
304 However, the shorter length of axis 1 indicates that pollen assemblages are more
305 similar overall.

306 For the plant assemblages, DCA axes 1 and 2 explain 34.04% and 26.77% of
307 the total variance respectively. Results for pollen assemblages are comparable, as
308 DCA axes 1 and 2 explain 32.16% and 30.66% of the total variance. Fitting
309 environmental variables to the ordination plots reveals that elevation (primarily related
310 to climate) is correlated with axis 1 for both datasets (plant assemblages: $r^2 = 0.8562$,
311 Supplementary Figure 2a; pollen assemblages: $r^2 = 0.5149$, Supplementary Figure 2d).
312 Canopy cover and distance to the sea are both aligned with axis 2. Canopy cover is
313 more linearly correlated with pollen ($r^2 = 0.5209$, Supplementary Figure 2e) than with
314 the plant assemblages ($r^2 = 0.4131$, Supplementary Figure 2b). Moreover, isolines of
315 canopy cover for the plant assemblages (Supplementary Figure 2b) suggest a quadratic
316 response, with the highest canopy cover at intermediate elevations. Distance to the sea
317 shows a considerably stronger correlation with the pollen assemblages ($r^2 = 0.6446$,
318 Supplementary Figure 2f) than with the plant assemblages ($r^2 = 0.304$, Supplementary
319 Figure 2c), suggesting that the distance to the sea, in principle a proxy for
320 continentality, affects pollen dispersal stronger than plant distribution. All the above
321 mentioned r^2 are significant at $p < 0.001$.

322 Comparing the DCA for the plant and pollen assemblages using Procrustes
323 analysis (Figure 4a) reveals that the ordinations significantly match (Procrustes sum-
324 of-squares $m^2 = 0.6393$; $p = 0.001$) but there are also some discrepancies. The
325 residuals of the analysis (Figure 4b) display the dissimilarities between all pairs of

326 plant and pollen assemblages. Exceptionally high dissimilarities (above the 75th
327 percentile) occur mostly in open vegetation sites at high elevation and/or surrounded
328 by pine- and oak-dominated stands (site numbers 8-10, 38-41, 43-44, 50, 55, 57-60),
329 probably due to greater deposition of long-distance transported pollen (Figure 4b;
330 Supplementary Table 3). More specifically, pollen composition differs more from the
331 plant assemblage when local and extra-local vegetation are different, and particularly
332 when the extra-local vegetation is dominated by high pollen producers such as pines
333 (9-10, 38-41, 43, 50, 55, 57, 59), oaks (50), or junipers (58). Most similar sampling
334 sites with the lowest Procrustes residuals (below 25th percentile) are those from maquis
335 and mixed deciduous forests, where the surrounding vegetation is quite homogeneous.

336 [insert Figure 4.]

337 Lake surface samples in the DCA (Figure 5) cluster together with grasslands
338 (PET), grasslands/mixed oak woodlands (KAS), mixed oak woodland (DOJ, IOA,
339 STR, ZAZ), mixed oak woodland/other shrublands (KOR, PRE, VEG), maquis
340 (VOL), and grasslands/beechn dominated stands (SMO). The sample of AMV is
341 outside of any hull, located between mixed oak woodland and maquis. The pollen
342 composition of PET (Petres) and KAS (Kastoria) show a dominance of Poaceae,
343 *Juniperus* t. but also higher abundances of *Quercus*, *Pinus sylvestris* t., and *Ostrya* t.
344 The latter differs from PET with higher percentages of shrubs and less herbs (Figure
345 6). ZAZ (Zazari) has a lower proportion of tree pollen and *Juniperus* t. but more
346 deciduous *Quercus* and grassland pollen (Figure 6). Based on the DCA plot, this
347 pollen assemblage points towards an open anthropogenic landscape with mixed oak
348 woodlands (Figure 2, 3, 5; Deza-Araujo et al., 2020). KOR (Koroneia), PRE (Prespa),
349 and VEG (Vegorit) surface pollen assemblages are co-dominated by *P. sylvestris* t.,
350 *Juniperus* t., *Quercus*, *Ostrya* t., *Fagus sylvatica* t., and Poaceae (Figure 6). DOJ
351 (Dojran), IOA (Ioannina), and STR (Strofilia) are characterized, besides *Olea*

352 *europaea* t., by Poaceae, *P. sylvestris* t., *Quercus* and *Juniperus* t. In comparison to
353 IOA and STR, DOJ records fewer *Q. ilex* t. and *P. sylvestris* t., but some more
354 deciduous *Quercus* and NAP (Figure 6). The pollen assemblage of VOL (Volvi) is
355 dominated by *Quercus*, *P. sylvestris* t., *Platanus*, *Olea europaea* t., and *Ostrya* t.
356 pollen. The abundance of Poaceae is lower compared to other lakes (Figure 6). The
357 pollen assemblage of SMO (Smolika) records a very high abundance of *P. sylvestris* t.
358 but also some *Juniperus* t. and lowland trees like evergreen and deciduous *Quercus*,
359 *Ostrya* t. or *Olea europaea* t. Finally, AMV (Amvrakia) has an outstanding proportion
360 of *Olea europaea* t. pollen (Figure 6), and this probably explains why it is not inside
361 any hull. Overall, pollen assemblages of lake surface samples closely reflect the
362 vegetation cover around the lakes, as indicated by their composition and the DCA
363 (Figures 5, 6). Likewise, pollen assemblages of lake surface samples generally match
364 the pollen composition of the terrestrial surface samples (Figure 5). The relatively
365 poor correspondence between pollen and vegetation composition found at Drakolimni
366 Smolika probably results from the low pollen production of the high-elevation open
367 vegetation around the lake, combined with the high pollen influx from the extensive
368 pinewoods that dominate at slightly lower elevation.

369 [insert Figure 5.]

370 [insert Figure 6.]

371 **3.3 Distinction, prediction, and indicator species**

372 The MCT for pollen has a considerably higher adjusted R^2 (41.59%) than for
373 plants (17.73%, Figure 7 a, b). Prediction accuracy is also higher for the pollen MCT
374 (26.4%) than for the plant MCT (12.1%). In both the plant and pollen MCTs (Figure
375 7a, b), the mixed deciduous forest and maquis vegetation types can be clearly
376 separated. *Q. coccifera* is the plant species that contributes most to differentiating

377 maquis from the other vegetation types (Figure 7a), whereas *Q. ilex* t. (which also
378 includes *Q. coccifera*) is the pollen counterpart (Figure 7b). Both *Quercus coccifera*
379 and *Q. ilex* are common components of evergreen forests and scrub communities
380 across most of the Mediterranean region (San-Miguel-Ayanz et al., 2016). *Fraxinus*
381 *ornus*, a rather widespread deciduous tree frequent in submediterranean forests (San-
382 Miguel-Ayanz et al., 2016), is the discriminant species separating mixed deciduous
383 forest from grassland, shrubland, and deciduous oak woodland pollen assemblages
384 (Figure 7b). Grassland, shrubland and oak woodland cannot be distinguished based on
385 their pollen assemblages (Figure 7b). *Pinus sylvestris* t., which mostly includes pollen
386 of several pine species widespread and abundant in mountainous areas of the region
387 (*Pinus sylvestris*, *P. nigra*, *P. heldreichii*), is the pollen type that discriminates pollen
388 assemblages of beech-dominated stands, forests with fir, and pine-dominated stands
389 (Figure 7b). In the plant dataset, *Q. frainetto*, usually found in pure stands or together
390 with *Fraxinus ornus*, *Ostrya carpinifolia* and other *Quercus* species in mixed
391 deciduous submediterranean forests, is the main species leading to the distinction
392 between deciduous oak woodlands on the one hand and grasslands and shrublands on
393 the other hand (Figure 7a). *Fagus sylvatica* and *Abies borisii-regis* are the discriminant
394 species for the vegetation types they dominate (Figure 7a).

395 [insert Figure 7.]

396 Maquis and mixed deciduous forest are the vegetation types that share the
397 highest number of indicator species in the plant and pollen MCTs: (i) maquis:
398 *Phillyrea*, *Pistacia*, *Cistus*, and *Q. coccifera* (*Q. ilex* t. in the pollen dataset); and (ii)
399 mixed deciduous forest: *Castanea sativa*, *Tilia*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Ostrya*, and *Corylus*
400 *avellana* (Supplementary Table 4). Those taxa are all listed among the characteristic
401 species of the maquis and deciduous forests, respectively, in classic vegetation maps
402 (Bohn et al., 2000/2003). Grassland, shrubland, and deciduous oak woodland

403 vegetation types share *Q. frainetto* (*Q. pubescens* t. in the pollen dataset) but differ in
404 their other indicator taxa. Poaceae were very important in the grassland and shrubland
405 plots, but, somehow unexpectedly, this taxon was not indicator of these vegetation
406 types in the plant MCT (Supplementary Table 4). *Fagus sylvatica* and *Abies borisii-*
407 *regis* are indicator species of their homonymous vegetation types in the plant dataset,
408 but not in the pollen MCT. In the plant MCT, *Pinus* spp. is neither present as
409 discriminant nor as indicator species, probably because it comprises several pine
410 species with different ecological behaviour (*P. heldreichii*, *P. nigra*, and *P. sylvestris*).

411 **3.4 Diversity trends and relationships**

412 Since trends in the various richness and evenness indices were similar
413 (Supplementary Table 5), we focus on the trends in the evenness-related index PIE,
414 the richness indices N0 or PRI, and the PIE-detrended richness DE-PRI. Examining
415 richness and evenness per vegetation type along an elevation gradient (Figure 8,
416 Supplementary Figures 3-5) suggests a decreasing trend in pollen (PRI, corresponding
417 to N0) and plant richness (N0) towards higher elevation vegetation types. Pollen and
418 plant evenness (PIE) are comparable: higher at the lowland sites, and becoming lower
419 for the temperate forests. Detrended richness (DE-PRI; Figure 8b, Supplementary
420 Figure 3b, 4b), as a function of PRI and PIE, shows much fewer oscillations than PRI,
421 especially for temperate forests. Results are similar for the full dataset and their
422 subsets. A closer comparison between pollen and plant diversity can be made for the
423 subset of trees and shrubs (Figure 8). It reveals that local trends in pollen and
424 vegetation PIE are inverted for the pine-dominated stands. Local pollen and plant data
425 suggest that the divergence between the two PIEs is caused by the overrepresentation
426 of pine pollen, which likely lowered pollen richness (PRI) if compared to vegetation
427 richness (N0; Figure 8). Such local pollen evenness distortion effects can also be

428 found at the sites where pine trees were present in the local to regional surrounding
429 (e.g. 9-10, 38, 43, 49-51, 55, 57, 38, temperate forests except sampling sites 8 and 60
430 with a dense beech canopy cover; Supplementary Table 1). As a consequence of
431 uneven conditions due to excessive pollen pine abundances (if compared to
432 vegetation), DE-PRI (which accounts for uneven conditions) is higher than PRI
433 (Figure 8). The comparison of PRI and DE-PRI with plant species richness suggests
434 that in such cases DE-PRI is able to partly correct for palynological distortions of
435 evenness (artificially low PRI is corrected to higher DE-PRI values; Figure 8a, b;
436 Supplementary Figures 3, 4)

437 [insert Figure 8.]

438 Correlation analyses between plant and pollen assemblages reveal no general
439 linkage between the diversity indices (Supplementary Table 5). The explanation of this
440 might be a combination of scaling (pollen catchment is far larger than the plots
441 surveyed for plant diversity) and data quality (herbaceous species were recorded only
442 semi-quantitatively) issues. However, if divided by pollen dispersal strategy, a
443 significant relationship between plant and pollen diversity indices appears for wind-
444 pollinated trees and shrubs (Supplementary Table 5).

445 **4. Discussion**

446 **4.1 Vegetation types and pollen**

447 Following a numerical approach similar to the previous study of Felde et al.
448 (2014b) in Norway, we show here that it is possible to distinguish most of the main
449 vegetation types of northern Greece using plant and pollen assemblages. Maquis
450 showed particularly distinct plant and pollen composition, making it readily
451 distinguishable from other Mediterranean vegetation types, in agreement with previous
452 studies (Fall, 2012; Glais et al., 2016). These results are in line with previous research

453 showing that pollen assemblages accurately reflected the main vegetation types in
454 Norway (Felde et al., 2014b), the Tibetan Plateau (Zhang et al., 2018) and Crete
455 (López-Sáez et al., 2019). However, our data from northern Greece show a poorer
456 performance of pollen assemblages to represent open vegetation as the correspondence
457 between plant and pollen assemblages declined further at the highest altitudes where
458 vegetation was more open (Figure 4b). Felde et al. (2014b) found similar issues in
459 Norway with an only slightly closer match between plant and pollen assemblages
460 ($m^2_{\text{Senn}} = 0.64$ vs $m^2_{\text{Felde}} = 0.57$). This may be due to high pollen producers like pines
461 overshadowing the pollen signature of other taxa, which in turn makes it also difficult
462 to differentiate among temperate (conifer) forests (Figures 2, 7). In the study area (as
463 elsewhere in the Mediterranean) pine species and pinewoods are key features in the
464 regional vegetation, thus *Pinus sylvestris* type cannot be simply excluded from the
465 calibration analyses. Indeed, pine forests were widespread around many of the beech-
466 dominated stands and mixed fir forests sites. Some of the temperate forests also had
467 pine trees in their composition, and mixed fir stands were mostly small. Several recent
468 studies have reported high shares of tree pollen, especially *Pinus*, in pollen
469 assemblages from grassland vegetation (e.g. Li et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2020; Zhang et
470 al., 2020). However, all these studies analysed moss polsters, which are prone to
471 trapping too high amounts of bisaccate pollen grains (Pardoe et al., 2010). Our results
472 highlight the need of collecting information about the extra-local and regional
473 vegetation when conducting calibration studies.

474 Reduced taxonomic resolution of pollen types compared to plant species may
475 also have affected pollen-inferred reconstructions of vegetation dynamics. This
476 problem arises especially in regions where different tree species with different
477 ecological requirements and habitats are represented by the same pollen type. For
478 example, we found three different pine species (i.e. *P. heldreichii*, *P. nigra*, and *P.*

479 *sylvestris*) in different habitats, but they were merged into a single vegetation type
480 because the species composition of their stands was very similar, so that merging was
481 indicated to avoid an excessive number of vegetation types. Although previous
482 research has provided promising results on the identification of pine pollen even to
483 species level in Iberia (Desprat et al., 2015), no similar study has been accomplished
484 in the north-eastern Mediterranean yet. This, alongside the rather different ecological
485 requirements of Mediterranean pines (Quézel and Médail, 2003), may explain why *P.*
486 *sylvestris* t. is not listed as indicator species in the MCT analysis. These issues are
487 more relevant in southern Europe because the diversity of tree species is higher
488 compared to northern Europe, and future research should clearly aim at refining the
489 taxonomic resolution of pollen identification for key taxa like pines and oaks,
490 following recent efforts in the Iberian Peninsula (Desprat et al., 2015; Muthreich et al.,
491 2020). Furthermore, (ancient) DNA studies may provide higher taxonomic resolution
492 (Birks and Birks, 2016; Parducci et al., 2017).

493 **4.2 The role of environmental variables**

494 Previous research has shown that elevation and landscape openness
495 (comparable to our canopy cover) are relevant in driving the composition of plant and
496 pollen assemblages (Glais et al., 2016; López-Sáez et al., 2018; Matthias et al., 2015;
497 Meltsov et al., 2013). Our results from northern Greece (Supplementary Figure 2a, b,
498 d, e) suggest that elevation, as surrogate for climate, is of greater importance than any
499 other environmental variable (see Supplementary Figure 2). Nevertheless, the
500 elevational gradient influences pollen assemblages less than expected, probably
501 because the upward transport of pollen “averages” the composition of pollen
502 assemblages at different elevations (e.g. pollen of *P. sylvestris* t. and *Quercus* in high-
503 elevation assemblages; Supplementary Figure 2; Akabane et al., 2020; Cañellas-Boltà

504 et al., 2009; Markgraf, 1980; Zhang et al., 2017). The effect of upward and long-
505 distance transported pollen deposition is even increased by reduced local pollen
506 production of open vegetation (Supplementary Figure 2e). Concerning canopy cover,
507 the hump-shaped curve of plant assemblage data show increasingly open vegetation at
508 high elevation and close to the seashore (Supplementary Figure 2b), with densest
509 vegetation at mid-elevations. Indeed, closed forests establish best at intermediate
510 elevations where moisture availability and temperature are most suitable for tree
511 growth and human disturbance is usually low because the usually steep terrain is not
512 particularly attractive for agriculture. In contrast, at coastal and lowland areas open
513 vegetation is primarily a result from long-lasting human impact (Hadjibiros, 2013) as
514 well as reduced summer moisture availability, while at high altitudes reduced
515 temperatures affect tree performance (Yang et al., 2006).

516 Previously published research showed that iso-thermality, a proxy for
517 continentality like distance to the sea, might also drive pollen composition (López-
518 Sáez et al., 2018; Reitalu et al., 2019). Our results also show that changes in plant and
519 particularly pollen composition are associated with the distance to the sea
520 (Supplementary Figure 2c, f). In our study region, the distance to the sea is probably
521 not only related to continentality but also implies decreasing human impact. Human
522 disturbance leads to decreased vegetation cover which in turn results in reduced local
523 to extra-regional pollen deposition. Based on the studied environmental variables, our
524 results therefore may suggest that climate together with human impact seems to drive
525 vegetation and pollen compositional changes.

526 **4.3 Comparison of terrestrial and lake sediment surface samples**

527 Comparing terrestrial and lake surface samples is essential to assess the utility
528 of pollen–vegetation comparisons for reconstructions from natural archives (e.g.

529 (Lisitsyna et al., 2012; Qin et al., 2015; Wilmshurst and McGlone, 2005). Here, we
530 assess for the first time the relationships between terrestrial and lake surface samples
531 in the Mediterranean region and can show a close analogy between them (Figure 5). In
532 addition, the lake surface samples seem to reflect the gradients in elevation and
533 distance to the sea, although to a lesser extent. Further, the residuals of the Procrustes
534 analysis (Figure 4) strongly suggest that pollen assemblages from terrestrial surface
535 samples also record extra-local to regional vegetation, as it was found in the lake
536 surface samples. This is more pronounced in open vegetation settings such as the tree
537 line ecotone and grasslands. Nonetheless, our findings and previous studies (Felde et
538 al., 2014a; Felde et al., 2016; Hagemans et al., 2019) hint that this association might
539 be weaker at high elevation or when surrounding vegetation is open (see SMO in
540 Figure 5). Thus, terrestrial surface sample pollen assemblages may also assist the
541 interpretation of fossil lake pollen sequences to reconstruct past vegetation. Despite
542 the amount of lakes sampled is not too high (12), these conclusions are robust enough
543 because they comprise a wide range of environmental conditions from the
544 mesomediterranean to the subalpine belt.

545 **4.4 Diversity**

546 Pollen richness (PRI) was argued to be a measure of plant species richness but
547 with a component of evenness (Odgaard, 2013), thus making it a good proxy for plant
548 diversity. Comparable trends in plant and pollen richness were found across
549 latitudinal, altitudinal, and continental transects (Connor et al., 2021; Felde et al.,
550 2016; Jantz et al., 2014; Reitalu et al., 2019; van der Sande et al., 2021). Discrepancies
551 between pollen and plant diversity were also found at higher latitudes and altitudes
552 presumably due to higher influence of long-distance transport (Felde et al., 2016; Jantz
553 et al., 2014; van der Sande et al., 2021). The data from northern Greece point to the

554 occurrence of decreasing trends in pollen and plant evenness (PIE) across the large
555 elevation gradient studied, suggesting that pollen evenness is generally a good proxy
556 for plant evenness. Common declining trends with increasing altitude also link plant
557 and pollen richness. In any case, they seem less pronounced than those between plant
558 and pollen evenness (Figures 8; Supplementary Figure 1). We assume that pollen
559 richness was affected by long-distance upward transport from the valley bottoms to the
560 mountain tops, an effect which is very well-known from other studies (e.g. Connor et
561 al., 2020; Felde et al., 2016; van der Sande et al., 2021). This effect, in combination
562 with the bias introduced by high pollen producers, may contribute to palynological
563 distortions if compared with species richness in vegetation relevées. Taken together, a
564 striking finding of our study is that pollen PIE and PRI are markedly distorted at sites
565 with pine occurrence, likely due to the high pollen production and dispersal ability of
566 pine species (Odgaard, 2001, 2013; Figure 8, Supplementary Table 1).

567 To counterbalance the over- and underrepresentation of certain pollen types,
568 correction factors are used (e.g. Davis, 1963; Prentice, 1985). However, many of them
569 apply to northern and central European vegetation. Alternatively, the exclusion of tree
570 pollen may lead to good results in Europe, since most trees are wind-pollinated and
571 their pollen is transported over long distances (Connor et al., 2021). This procedure
572 certainly needs sufficiently large pollen counts. It is noteworthy to use a method which
573 is appropriate to the scale and to the research question. For example, Jantz et al. (2014)
574 reported a better representation of pollen richness after combining smaller study plots
575 from the same vegetation belt. Within the summed-up areas, the pollen evenness was
576 higher. Connor et al. (2021) studied the diversity within smaller vegetation plots (1×1
577 m vs. 10×10 m in this study). The exclusion of trees thus may seem reasonable to
578 detect diversity trend. However, lake sediment samples might capture wider areas than
579 terrestrial surface samples and an exclusion might be misleading. Furthermore, trees

580 are key features at our sampling sites and in the regional vegetation and makes an
581 exclusion of tree pollen unjustifiable. Alternatively, evenness-detrended palynological
582 richness (DE-PRI) might be applied to reduce the effect of palynological evenness
583 distortions (Colombaroli and Tinner, 2013). Indeed, DE-PRI might locally correct
584 biases, for instance increasing richness in samples with overrepresentation of pine
585 pollen. Indeed, DE-PRI reflects N0 better than PRI within the pine-dominated stands
586 (Figure 8). However, our vegetation records suggest that the discrepancies between
587 DE-PRI and PRI might either arise from underrepresented plant evenness or
588 underrepresented plant richness (Figure 8). The unknown distortion effects between
589 DE-PRI and PRI highlight that DE-PRI should be seen as a check for PRI, with a good
590 agreement between PRI and DE-PRI suggesting that the reconstructed richness
591 estimates are robust and unaffected by evenness effects (see discussion in Colombaroli
592 and Tinner, 2013).

593 **5. Conclusion**

594 This study evaluated the correspondence between vegetation type, plant
595 diversity and pollen, and the use of pollen analysis as proxy for past vegetation
596 dynamics and diversity in northern Greece, a hotspot of plant diversity and endemism.
597 We showed that it is possible to discern the main vegetation types based on pollen
598 assemblages. Further, the observed linkages of terrestrial surface samples with lake
599 surface samples are essential to generalise the application of our results to lake
600 sediments. Increasing discrepancies between vegetation and pollen assemblages are
601 detected with rising pollen catchment size (higher altitudes, open vegetation) but also
602 due to high pollen producers (e.g. pines). To weaken such discrepancies, *P. sylvestris*
603 t. pollen might be excluded from the pollen sum, but given its relevance in the
604 Mediterranean vegetation we rather suggest checking the presence of rare

605 accompanying taxa or applying complementary approaches such as aDNA (Birks and
606 Birks, 2016; Gosling et al., 2018; Morales-Molino et al., 2020b; Parducci et al., 2017).
607 With enhanced taxonomic resolution it will be possible to refine the reconstruction of
608 diversity patterns along environmental gradients or through time. We propose that
609 plant and pollen diversity, as captured by richness and evenness measures, show a
610 rather close relationship over wide spatial scales. Our Greek case study may thus
611 contribute to refine reconstructions of past Mediterranean vegetation dynamics. Future
612 studies may investigate the role of pollen productivity and dispersal in creating marked
613 discrepancies and biases between plant and pollen diversity measures (evenness,
614 richness), as observed for pines in this study. Similar distortions might be caused by
615 other strong pollen producers (e.g. *Corylus*, *Betula*, *Alnus*), potentially affecting
616 pollen-based diversity reconstructions. This hypothesis would need to be verified in
617 temperate or boreal vegetation types, in which such woody plants are important.

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640 **7. Declaration of conflicting interests**

641 The Authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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963

10. Figures

966 **Figure 1:** Overview of the study sampling sites (colored symbols with sampling numbers; legend on the right): a) location
 967 on a map of Greece together with the location of the 12 lakes (yellow stars) for comparing their surface sediments with
 968 terrestrial surface samples, b) distribution according to their elevation and vegetation type shown as boxplots (black line =
 969 median elevation per vegetation type), and c) pictures showing the typical appearance of the vegetation types (photo credits:
 970 C. Morales-Molino). Map made with QGIS using Natural Earth Data and SRTM digital elevation data.

977 **Figure 3:** Percentage pollen diagram of the surface samples from northern Greece (ordered according to vegetation types):
 978 selected herbs and ferns. White bars show 10x exaggerations. Shown herbs and ferns were selected based on their value as
 979 indicator species or their general relevance along the sites. Within each vegetation type, sampling sites are arranged by
 980 increasing elevation.

982 **Figure 4:** Procrustes analysis: a) Ordination diagram showing errors in two-dimensional space for the comparison of DCA
 983 ordinations between paired sites (plant vs pollen assemblages; see Supplementary Figure 2). Similarity between paired sites
 984 is represented by the length of the arrows, with short arrows indicating high similarity and long arrows low similarity.
 985 Procrustes sum of squares ($m^2 = 0.6393$) measures the similarity between the two ordinations with 0 being identical
 986 ordinations, 1 being totally different ordinations.
 987 b) Impulse diagram showing the Procrustes errors (Procrustes residuals) for each sampling site (site number) highlighted in
 988 the corresponding color of each vegetation type. Solid and dashed horizontal lines indicate median and 25th- and 75th-
 989 quantiles of the residual distribution, respectively.
 990

992 **Figure 5:** Ordination diagram showing the result of the Detrended Correspondence Analysis (DCA) for the pollen dataset (as
 993 in Supplementary Figure 2d-f). The 12 lake sediment surface samples (asterisks) are passively added to the ordination to
 994 assess the modern pollen representation of these sediments (AMV: Limni Amvrakia; DOJ: Limni Doirani; IOA: Limni
 995 Ioannina; KAS: Limni Kastoria; KOR: Limni Koroneia; PET: Limni Petres; PRE: Limni Megali Prespa; SMO: Drakolimni
 996 Smolika; STR: Limni Strofilia/Prokopou; VEG: Limni Vegoritisi; VOL: Limni Volvi; ZAZ: Limni Zazari).
 997

1005 **Figure 7:** Multivariate Classification Tree (MCT) of a) the plant and b) the pollen assemblage data with the eight vegetation
 1006 types as response variables. The tree individually splits the sampling sites based on their different plant and pollen
 1007 assemblages, respectively. Each split includes the split number, its coefficient of determination (r^2), and the discriminant
 1008 species/taxa if available. Number of sampling sites within a leaf (n) and leaf number noted below the leaves. Adjusted R², R²,
 1009 error, cross-validated error (CV Error), and standard error (SE) for the entire model are depicted below the tree. Prediction
 1010 accuracy of the model is 1 – CV Error, i.e. 0.121 in (a) and 0.261 in (b).
 1011 Indicator species for each leaf (leaves 1 – 7 for plants, leaves 1 – 4 for pollen) are listed together with its indicator value in
 1012 Supplementary Table 4.

Pollen subset of trees and shrubs

Plant subset of trees and shrubs

1014 **Figure 8:** a) Pollen richness [PRI, orange] with Probability of Interspecific Encounter (PIE) evenness for pollen [purple] and
 1015 b) detrended pollen richness [DE-PRI, red] for the subset trees and shrubs organised within same vegetation types along
 1016 increasing elevation (as in Figure 1). c) Plant richness [N0, green] with Probability of Interspecific Encounter (PIE) evenness
 1017 for plants [darkblue] for the subset trees and shrubs organised within same vegetation groups along increasing elevation (as in
 1018 Figure 1).
 1019

1020

11. Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1: Sampling sites in northern Greece and its main features.

Site number	Sampling site	Geographical coordinates	Elevation [m a.s.l.]	Distance to the sea [km]; rounded to 10 m	Vegetation type	Canopy cover (in 5% steps)	Local vegetation; Extra-local vegetation
1	Sithonia_01	39°57'57.7"N 23°57'08.6"E	111	1.480	Maquis	0%	Maquis; some mixed pine stands nearby
2	Sithonia_03	39°57'59.8"N 23°57'28.0"E	67	1.050	Maquis	0%	Phrygana; Maquis and groves of <i>Olea europaea</i> nearby
3	Sithonia_05	39°57'51.0"N 23°57'35.0"E	49	0.960	Maquis	0%	Maquis; with <i>Fraxinus ornus</i> and <i>Quercus ilex</i> nearby
4	Sithonia_06	40°00'46.4"N 23°59'01.9"E	64	1.670	Maquis	0%	Maquis; heavily overgrazed maquis and grassland nearby
5	Polygyros_07	40°22'17.7"N 23°28'04.4"E	790	10.560	Deciduous Oak Woodland	70%	Mixed oak woodland; pine afforestation nearby
6	Polygyros_08	40°22'23.6"N 23°28'07.5"E	783	10.750	Pine-dominated stand	90%	<i>Pinus nigra</i> afforestation; mixed oak woodland nearby
7	Polygyros_10	40°24'41.9"N 23°29'19.8"E	753	15.320	Deciduous Oak Woodland	85%	<i>Quercus frainetto</i> woodland with <i>Fagus sylvatica</i> and <i>Taxus baccata</i> ; mixed pine woodland with <i>Fagus sylvatica</i> nearby
8	Polygyros_11	40°24'34.3"N 23°29'24.7"E	785	15.120	Beech-dominated stand	90%	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i> stand with mixed trees - incl. <i>Sambucus nigra</i> , <i>Ilex aquifolium</i> ; <i>Quercus frainetto</i> woodland with <i>Fagus sylvatica</i> nearby
9	Polygyros_12	40°23'33.3"N 23°28'04.3"E	842	12.840	Deciduous Oak Woodland	90%	<i>Quercus frainetto</i> woodland with <i>Fagus sylvatica</i> ; pine woodland nearby
10	Polygyros_13	40°23'28.7"N 23°28'07.5"E	808	12.710	Deciduous Oak Woodland	90%	<i>Quercus frainetto</i> woodland; pine woodland and deciduous forests nearby

11	Polygyros_14	40°23'13.7"N 23°27'13.9"E	665	12.060	Maquis	0%	Maquis with deciduous component; riparian forest nearby
12	Katsika_15	40°22'34.7"N 23°10'13.2"E	374	9.980	Maquis	0%	Maquis; with <i>Fraxinus ornus</i> , and conifer afforestation nearby
13	Katsika_16	40°22'36.6"N 23°10'21.8"E	407	10.160	Maquis	0%	Maquis; with <i>Fraxinus ornus</i> , and conifer afforestation nearby
14	Katsika_17	40°22'36.0"N 23°10'24.0"E	419	10.170	Maquis	0%	Maquis; conifer afforestation nearby
15	Katsika_18	40°22'34.4"N 23°10'20.1"E	402	10.080	Maquis	0%	Maquis; conifer afforestation and a seasonal river nearby
16	Litochoro_19	40°05'06.2"N 22°24'27.4"E	1071	13.590	Beech-dominated stand	100%	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i> and mixed pine forest
17	Litochoro_20	40°05'11.5"N 22°24'30.9"E	1045	13.460	Mixed fir forest	100%	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i> and <i>Abies borisii-regis</i> forest with some <i>Pinus nigra</i> ; some <i>Pinus heldreichii</i> nearby
18	Litochoro_21	40°05'12.3"N 22°24'35.3"E	1053	13.350	Mixed fir forest	100%	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i> , <i>Abies borisii-regis</i> and mixed pine forest; mixed forests
19	Litochoro_22	40°05'14.2"N 22°24'38.7"E	1024	13.260	Pine-dominated stand	85%	<i>Pinus nigra</i> forest with <i>Fagus sylvatica</i> and <i>Buxus sempervirens</i> ; mixed pine forests
20	Litochoro_23	40°05'22.2"N 22°25'02.5"E	930	12.630	Pine-dominated stand	50%	<i>Pinus nigra</i> forest with some <i>Pinus heldreichii</i> , <i>Fagus sylvatica</i> , and <i>Abies borisii-regis</i>
21	Litochoro_24	40°05'39.1"N 22°26'21.4"E	775	10.710	Beech-dominated stand	100%	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i> and <i>Pinus nigra</i> forest; with some <i>Abies borisii-regis</i> and <i>Taxus baccata</i> nearby
22	Litochoro_25	40°05'39.2"N 22°27'19.3"E	646	9.430	Mixed Deciduous Forest	85%	Submediterranean mixed deciduous forest with <i>Ostrya carpinifolia</i> , <i>Buxus sempervirens</i> , and evergreens; <i>Fagus</i>

							<i>sylvatica</i> and <i>Pinus nigra</i> stands in mid-range
23	Litochoro_26	40°05'30.4"N 22°27'34.6"E	832	9.210	Mixed Deciduous Forest	95%	Mixed forest with <i>Quercus ilex</i> , <i>Abies borisii-regis</i> , and <i>Ostrya carpinifolia</i> ; mixed forest composed of temperate deciduous and evergreen trees and conifers
24	Litochoro_27	40°06'25.2"N 22°30'04.8"E	293	5.270	Maquis	95%	Maquis; mixed pines, <i>Picea abies</i> , and a football stadium nearby
25	Ossa_29	39°51'29.9"N 22°43'27.1"E	242	2.310	Mixed Deciduous Forest	80%	Riparian forest with <i>Platanus orientalis</i> , <i>Fraxinus ornus</i> , <i>Corylus avellana</i> , and lianes
26	Ossa_30	39°51'32.5"N 22°43'36.7"E	244	2.110	Mixed Deciduous Forest	95%	Mixed deciduous forest with <i>Fraxinus ornus</i> and several evergreen taxa
27	Ossa_31	39°51'29.0"N 22°43'55.6"E	240	1.900	Mixed Deciduous Forest	100%	Mixed deciduous forest with <i>Castanea sativa</i> from an abandoned chestnut orchard
28	Ossa_32	39°51'31.6"N 22°43'59.4"E	214	1.780	Mixed Deciduous Forest	95%	Mixed deciduous forest with <i>Castanea sativa</i> , <i>Cercis siliquastrum</i> , and <i>Celtis australis</i>
29	Ossa_33	39°51'35.1"N 22°44'12.9"E	161	1.480	Mixed Deciduous Forest	95%	Mixed deciduous forest with <i>Tilia platyphyllos</i>
30	AgiaKori_34	40°08'43.8"N 22°24'06.2"E	986	12.610	Pine-dominated stand	95%	<i>Pinus nigra</i> forest with <i>Buxus sempervirens</i> , <i>Ilex aquifolium</i> , and other evergreens; mixed deciduous forest, agricultural fields, and meadows nearby
31	AgiaKori_35	40°08'48.9"N 22°23'30.4"E	951	13.460	Pine-dominated stand	90%	<i>Pinus nigra</i> forest with <i>Fagus sylvatica</i> , <i>Abies borisii-regis</i> , and few <i>Taxus baccata</i>
32	AgiaKori_36	40°09'17.5"N 22°23'21.9"E	819	13.710	Pine-dominated stand	80%	<i>Pinus nigra</i> and <i>Arbutus andrachne</i> stand

33	AgiaKori_37	40°09'26.4"N 22°23'33.3"E	728	13.450	Maquis	45%	Maquis with <i>Arbutus andrachne</i> ; <i>Pinus nigra</i> forest nearby
34	AgiaKori_38	40°09'32.5"N 22°23'53.1"E	577	13.000	Pine-dominated stand	80%	<i>Pinus nigra</i> forest with plants characteristic for maquis
35	AgiaKori_39	40°09'48.0"N 22°24'00.3"E	456	12.870	Mixed Deciduous Forest	95%	<i>Quercus ilex</i> woodland with deciduous trees
36	AgiaKori_40	40°09'57.7"N 22°23'51.8"E	390	13.100	Maquis	70%	Open maquis; <i>Platanus orientalis</i> nearby
37	Prionia_41	40°04'54.7"N 22°23'48.8"E	1444	14.570	Beech-dominated stand	95%	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i> , <i>Pinus heldreichii</i> and <i>P. nigra</i> forest
38	Prionia_42	40°04'33.1"N 22°21'52.9"E	2449	17.370	Grassland	0%	Alpine meadow with krummholz (<i>Pinus heldreichii</i>)
39	Prionia_43	40°04'35.2"N 22°22'10.6"E	2267	16.950	Pine-dominated stand	55%	<i>Pinus heldreichii</i> treeline
40	Prionia_44	40°04'53.5"N 22°22'19.8"E	2003	16.560	Pine-dominated stand	70%	<i>Pinus heldreichii</i> timberline; rocky grassland nearby
41	Prionia_45	40°04'54.3"N 22°22'54.0"E	1634	15.790	Pine-dominated stand	75%	<i>Pinus heldreichii</i> forest; with subalpine conifers (<i>Abies borisii-regis</i>) and <i>Ostrya carpinifolia</i> nearby
42	Kokkinopylos_46	40°04'27.7"N 22°16'54.7"E	1758	24.100	Mixed fir forest	80%	<i>Pinus nigra</i> and <i>Abies borisii-regis</i> close to timberline; with deciduous trees and <i>Buxus sempervirens</i> nearby
43	Kokkinopylos_47	40°04'50.4"N 22°16'41.3"E	1592	24.190	Shrubland	5%	<i>Buxus</i> -dominated shrubland in a snow avalanche track; Shrubland and <i>Pinus nigra</i> forest with <i>Buxus sempervirens</i> and <i>Ostrya carpinifolia</i> nearby

44	Kokkinopylos_48	40°04'56.2"N 22°16'15.3"E	1451	24.730	Mixed fir forest	100%	Small and young <i>Abies borisii-regis</i> stand; Shrubland with <i>Acer hyrcanum</i> , <i>Ostrya carpinifolia</i> , and <i>Buxus sempervirens</i> nearby
45	Kokkinopylos_49	40°05'00.7"N 22°16'08.2"E	1402	24.850	Mixed fir forest	100%	<i>Abies borisii-regis</i> stand; shrubland and mixed forest of <i>Acer hyrcanum</i> , <i>Ostrya carpinifolia</i> , <i>Buxus sempervirens</i> , and <i>Pinus nigra</i> nearby
46	Kokkinopylos_50	40°05'19.9"N 22°15'25.0"E	1353	25.690	Maquis	0%	Maquis; <i>Pinus nigra</i> forest nearby
47	LakeKastoria_52	40°35'15.9"N 21°17'53.5"E	799	109.340	Deciduous Oak Woodland	55%	Open deciduous oak woodland; mixed pine woodland and agricultural fields nearby
48	LakeKastoria_55	40°30'08.2"N 21°21'29.4"E	695	103.590	Shrubland	25%	Abandoned field with <i>Paliurus spina-christi</i>
49	LakeZazari_57	40°37'11.5"N 21°32'11.1"E	614	89.920	Deciduous Oak Woodland	35%	Open deciduous oak woodland; mixed pine woodland, agricultural fields, and <i>Phragmites australis</i> belt nearby
50	LakeZazari_58	40°37'01.2"N 21°32'38.0"E	631	89.240	Deciduous Oak Woodland	10%	Open deciduous oak woodland; mixed pine woodland, heavily overgrazed agricultural fields, and <i>Phragmites australis</i> belt nearby
51	LakeVegoritida_59	40°48'23.0"N 21°46'45.2"E	638	77.390	Deciduous Oak Woodland	20%	Open deciduous oak woodland; open mixed pine woodland and a road nearby
52	LakeVegoritida_61	40°42'18.4"N 21°46'21.6"E	551	73.170	Shrubland	0%	Shibljak; shrubland, agricultural fields with fruit trees, and coastal vegetation nearby
53	LakeVegoritida_62	40°47'00.1"N 21°46'27.7"E	532	76.560	Shrubland	35%	Shibljak; mixed deciduous woodland and coastal vegetation nearby
54	LakePetres_63	40°42'48.9"N 21°40'38.4"E	573	81.060	Grassland	0%	Ruderal grassland; lakeshore vegetation nearby

55	LakePetres_64	40°44'07.0"N 21°40'37.1"E	589	81.910	Grassland	0%	Steppic grassland with <i>Juniperus communis</i> and few <i>Juniperus oxycedrus</i> ; <i>Phragmites australis</i> reedbed nearby
56	LakePetres_65	40°46'15.8"N 21°42'07.2"E	758	81.480	Grassland	0%	Steppic grassland with <i>Juniperus communis</i> and few <i>Juniperus oxycedrus</i> ; <i>Quercus trojana</i> , overgrazed meadows, and fruit trees nearby
57	SkiResort_66	40°54'43.6"N 21°48'56.3"E	2030	81.210	Grassland	0%	Alpine meadow with <i>Juniperus communis</i> ssp. <i>nana</i> ; some mires nearby
58	SkiResort_67	40°53'49.4"N 21°49'11.9"E	1830	79.910	Pine-dominated stand	45%	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i> stand at treeline ecotone
59	SkiResort_68	40°53'00.8"N 21°48'19.8"E	1667	80.030	Pine-dominated stand	70%	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i> afforestation; deciduous trees nearby
60	SkiResort_69	40°51'57.3"N 21°46'06.7"E	1532	81.540	Beech-dominated stand	100%	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i> forest; meadows far away
61	SkiResort_70	40°50'06.9"N 21°48'09.5"E	646	77.290	Deciduous Oak Woodland	60%	Open deciduous oak woodland; mixed pine woodland and orchards nearby

Supplementary Table 2: Overview of the 12 lake sites

Lake	Abbreviation	Vegetation types around the lake	Coring year	Latitude (N)	Longitude (E)	Elevation (m a.s.l)	Water depth (m)	Coring device	Pollen analyst
Limni Amvrakia	AMV	<i>Olea europaea</i> groves, maquis, oak woodlands, agricultural fields	2020	38°43'48.0"	21°11'18.0"	14	3	Kajak gravity corer	CS
Limni Doirani	DOJ	Agricultural fields, pine woods	2020	41°12'18.1"	22°45'15.8"	140	9	Kajak gravity corer	CS
Limni Ioannina	IOA	Agricultural fields, shrublands, pine afforestations; on the surrounding hills: heavily grazed maquis, garrigue	2020	39°40'21.0"	20°54'10.8"	469	5	Kajak gravity corer	CS
Limni Kastoria	KAS16	Grasslands, orchards, agricultural fields, degraded shrublands on the hills: steppic grassland, deciduous oak woods, pine afforestations	2016	40°31'57.7"	21°17'19.6"	632	6	UWITEC gravity corer	CS
Limni Koroneia	KOR	Grasslands, agricultural fields, shrublands	2020	40°41'36.0"	23°08'48.0"	64	1	Kajak gravity corer	CS
Limni Petres	PET16	Steppic grassland with <i>Juniperus</i>	2016	40°43'54.6"	21°42'00.8"	575	3.5	UWITEC gravity corer	CS
Limni Megali Prespa	PRE	Mixed deciduous oak woodlands; on the hills, beech forests and montane conifer forests	2020	40°49'54.0"	21°05'36.0"	842	6	Kajak gravity corer	CS
Drakolimni Smolika	SMO	Alpine grassland, open pine stands	2020	40°05'24.2"	20°54'31.8"	2160	3.2	Kajak gravity corer	CS
Limni Strofilita/ Prokopou	STR	Agricultural fields, <i>Olea europaea</i> groves, grasslands, garrigue	2020	38°09'15.0"	21°23'36.0"	0	2	Kajak gravity corer	CS
Limni Vegorititis	VEG16	Orchards, shibljak, steppic grasslands, degraded deciduous oak woodlands	2016	40°46'59"	21°49'20"	520	18.5	UWITEC gravity corer	JvL
Limni Volvi	VOL	Maquis, agricultural fields	2020	40°39'51.9"	23°32'30.8"	30	19.3	UWITEC gravity corer	CS
Limni Zazari	ZAZ16	Grasslands, cereal fields, orchards, riparian stands, shrubland; on the hills: oak woodlands	2016	40°37'27.4"	21°33'09.1"	606	6.3	UWITEC gravity corer	CMM

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Supplementary Table 3: Site numbers with exceptional high residuals in the Procrustes analysis with its dominant characteristics in local and extra-local vegetation and pollen record. (t. = type)

Site number	Dominant characteristics in local vegetation	Dominant characteristics in extra-local vegetation	Dominant characteristics in pollen record
8, 60	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	<i>Quercus frainetto</i> with <i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	<i>Quercus pubescens</i> t., <i>Q. ilex</i> t., <i>Castanea sativa</i> , <i>Platanus</i> , <i>Juniperus</i> t.; low in <i>Pinus sylvestris</i> t.
9, 10	Deciduous oak woodland	<i>Pinus</i> spp.	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i> t.
38, 57	Alpine grassland	Alpine grassland	Pollen from treeline (<i>Pinus sylvestris</i> t.), deciduous oak woodland, mixed deciduous forest
39, 40, 58	Around timberline with <i>Pinus</i> spp.	Around timberline with <i>Pinus</i> spp.	Different herb composition compared to other samples of pine-dominated stands
41, 59	<i>Pinus</i> spp. and other conifers, rather sparse forests	<i>Pinus</i> spp. and other conifers, rather sparse forests	Different herb composition compared to other samples of pine-dominated stands
43	<i>Buxus</i> shrubland	<i>Pinus</i> spp.	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i> t. and <i>Quercus</i>
44	Young <i>Abies borisii-regis</i> stand	Shrubland of <i>Buxus sempervirens</i> and mixed forest	Slightly lower in <i>Pinus sylvestris</i> t.; higher counts of <i>Abies</i> , <i>Ostrya</i> , <i>Quercus ilex</i> t and <i>Juniperus</i> t
55	Steppic grassland	Steppic grassland	Arboreal pollen, mainly from fruit trees
60	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	<i>Juniperus</i> t., <i>Castanea sativa</i> , <i>Platanus</i> , Poaceae; low abundance of <i>Pinus sylvestris</i> t.

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1030 **Supplementary Table 4:** Indicator species with their indicator values (IndVal) for the multivariate classification trees of the
 1031 plant and pollen assemblage datasets, identified using the wrapper function MRT() of the MVPARTwrap package in R
 1032 (Ouellette MH and Legendre P, 2013). The most important indicator species are listed for each leaf (threshold above 20%
 1033 IndVal, p-value < 0.05). (t. = type)

MRT Indicator Species (Indicator Value) for the plant dataset	MRT Indicator Species (Indicator Value) for the pollen dataset
leaf 1 <i>Sanicula europaea</i> (0.6994) <i>Fagus sylvatica</i> (0.626) <i>Rosa</i> sp (0.461) <i>Symphytum</i> sp (.400) <i>Viola riviniana/reichenbachiana</i> (0.353) <i>Primula vulgaris</i> (0.271) <i>Daphne laureola</i> (0.259)	leaf 1 <i>Pinus sylvestris</i> t. (0.419) Brassicaceae undiff. (0.376)
leaf 2 <i>Abies borisii-regis</i> (0.869) <i>Hypopitys monotropa</i> ssp <i>monotropa</i> (0.400) <i>Acer hyrcanum</i> (0.353) <i>Euonymus latifolius</i> (0.329)	leaf 2 <i>Pistacia</i> (0.561) <i>Phillyrea</i> (0.531) <i>Quercus ilex</i> t. (0.444) <i>Arbutus</i> t. (0.432) <i>Erica</i> t. (0.365) <i>Olea europaea</i> (0.352) <i>Cistus</i> (0.280) <i>Ambrosia artemisaefolia</i> t. (0.257) <i>Aster/Senecio</i> t. (0.188)
leaf 3 <i>Quercus frainetto</i> (0.590) <i>Carpinus orientalis</i> (0.331) <i>Clinopodium vulgare</i> (0.294)	leaf 3 <i>Solanum dulcamara</i> (0.625) <i>Castanea sativa</i> (0.546) <i>Tilia</i> (0.532)
leaf 4 <i>Eryngium</i> cf <i>campestre</i> (0.444) <i>Rhamnus saxatilis</i> (0.300) woody <i>Galium</i> sp (0.284)	<i>Platanus</i> (0.513) <i>Fraxinus ornus</i> (0.495) <i>Corylus</i> (0.458) <i>Rubus</i> (0.415) <i>Ostrya</i> t. (0.359) <i>Hedera helix</i> (0.316)
leaf 5 <i>Geranium sanguineum</i> (0.333) <i>Thalictrum</i> sp (0.333) <i>Lonicera etrusca</i> (0.264)	leaf 4 <i>Artemisia</i> (0.530) <i>Quercus pubescens</i> t. (0.480) <i>Rumex acetosa/R. acetosella</i> t. (0.462) Caryophyllaceae undiff. (0.398) Poaceae (0.361) Apiaceae undiff. (0.344) <i>Juniperus</i> t. (0.342) <i>Typha angustifolia</i> t. (0.304) <i>Quercus cerris</i> t. (0.298) <i>Sanguisorba minor</i> t. (0.286) <i>Ranunculus acris</i> t. (0.260) <i>Achillea</i> t. (0.224)
leaf 6 <i>Dioscorea communis</i> (0.625) <i>Tilia platyphyllos</i> (0.625) <i>Fraxinus ornus</i> (0.537) <i>Cornus sanguinea</i> (0.523) <i>Polystichum setiferum</i> (0.500) <i>Asplenium adiantum nigrum/onopteris</i> (0.462) Boraginaceae (0.401) <i>Ostrya carpinifolia</i> (0.392) <i>Prunus</i> sp (0.375) <i>Celtis australis</i> (0.286) <i>Quercus ilex</i> (0.276) <i>Clematis vitalba</i> (0.265) <i>Castanea sativa</i> (0.250) <i>Tilia tomentosa</i> (0.250) <i>Corylus avellana</i> (0.250) <i>Laurus nobilis</i> (0.250) <i>Calystegia</i> sp (0.250) <i>Polypodium</i> sp (0.250)	
leaf 7	

Phillyrea latifolia (0.613)
Quercus coccifera (0.610)
Asparagus acutifolius (0.338)
Calicotome villosa (0.308)
Pistacia lentiscus (0.308)
Teucrium flavum (0.308)
Cistus creticus (0.291)
Rhamnus alaternus (0.231)

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Supplementary Table 5: Pearson product-moment correlation coefficients (r) between plant diversity indices and pollen diversity indices for the different datasets (full dataset: all recorded plants or counted pollen; subset: trees and shrubs of the plant or pollen dataset; sub-subset: wind-pollinated trees and shrubs of the plant or pollen dataset); without PIE-detrended pollen richness (PRI) and with PIE-detrended pollen richness (DE-PRI). Significance levels for p-values: light blue <0.05, blue <0.01, dark blue <0.0001. N0 – N2: Hill numbers 1 – 3; PIE: Hurlbert’s Probability of Interspecific Encounter; E0, modE0, E1, modE1, E3: Hill-number derived evenness measures (Felde et al. 2016); N1/DE-PRI and modN1/modDE-PRI are the detrended versions of the pollen E1 and modE1, respectively.

<i>full dataset</i>	Pollen N0	Pollen DE-PRI	Pollen N1	Pollen N2	Pollen PIE	Pollen E0	Pollen modE0	Pollen E1	Pollen modE1	Pollen N1/DE-PRI	Pollen modN1/modDE-PRI	Pollen E3
Plant N0	-0.148	0.040	-0.120	-0.086	-0.230	0.110	-0.149	-0.127	-0.136	-0.131	-0.130	-0.169
Plant N1	-0.083	-0.124	-0.019	-0.010	-0.004	-0.032	-0.004	0.033	0.025	0.018	0.014	-0.031
Plant N2	-0.079	-0.113	-0.032	-0.027	-0.008	-0.048	-0.014	0.012	0.007	0.000	-0.004	-0.038
Plant PIE	-0.078	-0.101	-0.020	-0.007	-0.013	0.051	0.016	0.015	0.005	-0.001	-0.006	-0.042
Plant E0	0.091	-0.015	0.063	0.045	0.131	-0.055	0.082	0.072	0.081	0.084	0.086	0.089
Plant modE0	-0.072	-0.025	-0.108	-0.110	-0.073	-0.056	-0.078	-0.117	-0.115	-0.124	-0.125	-0.095
Plant E1	-0.013	-0.141	0.015	0.010	0.106	-0.064	0.079	0.069	0.068	0.062	0.057	0.023
Plant modE1	-0.019	-0.135	0.009	0.006	0.092	-0.056	0.070	0.059	0.058	0.052	0.047	0.014
Plant E3	-0.070	-0.125	0.056	0.076	0.017	0.061	0.048	0.120	0.105	0.100	0.095	0.016
<i>subset</i>	Pollen N0	Pollen DE-PRI	Pollen N1	Pollen N2	Pollen PIE	Pollen E0	Pollen modE0	Pollen E1	Pollen modE1	Pollen N1/DE-PRI	Pollen modN1/modDE-PRI	Pollen E3
Plant N0	0.142	0.216	0.037	0.005	0.004	-0.213	-0.095	-0.081	-0.049	-0.068	-0.060	0.108
Plant N1	0.176	0.207	0.073	0.038	0.056	-0.216	-0.049	-0.036	-0.001	-0.019	-0.011	0.146
Plant N2	0.174	0.189	0.074	0.036	0.067	-0.226	-0.042	-0.028	0.008	-0.009	-0.002	0.150
Plant PIE	0.140	0.145	0.044	0.016	0.061	-0.154	-0.009	-0.039	-0.012	-0.032	-0.030	0.104
Plant E0	-0.001	-0.123	0.057	0.050	0.099	-0.009	0.084	0.118	0.113	0.120	0.119	0.063
Plant modE0	0.023	-0.005	0.000	-0.017	0.034	-0.090	-0.002	-0.004	0.005	0.000	0.001	0.039
Plant E1	0.128	-0.064	0.151	0.141	0.216	-0.035	0.185	0.192	0.204	0.207	0.207	0.154
Plant modE1	0.144	0.019	0.109	0.087	0.170	-0.112	0.116	0.101	0.125	0.118	0.119	0.143
Plant E3	0.151	0.238	0.057	0.035	-0.001	-0.134	-0.068	-0.063	-0.037	-0.054	-0.046	0.099
<i>sub-subset</i>	Pollen N0	Pollen DE-PRI	Pollen N1	Pollen N2	Pollen PIE	Pollen E0	Pollen modE0	Pollen E1	Pollen modE1	Pollen N1/DE-PRI	Pollen modN1/modDE-PRI	Pollen E3
Plant N0	-0.106	0.106	-0.282	-0.302	-0.240	-0.260	-0.273	-0.335	-0.313	-0.328	-0.326	-0.120
Plant N1	0.004	0.106	-0.138	-0.170	-0.088	-0.263	-0.157	-0.191	-0.162	-0.182	-0.179	0.024
Plant N2	0.033	0.103	-0.093	-0.127	-0.045	-0.255	-0.121	-0.142	-0.112	-0.132	-0.128	0.064
Plant PIE	0.021	0.116	-0.124	-0.149	-0.077	-0.225	-0.130	-0.183	-0.155	-0.176	-0.173	0.005
Plant E0	0.212	-0.041	0.342	0.332	0.332	0.078	0.275	0.373	0.378	0.381	0.387	0.281
Plant modE0	0.277	0.041	0.291	0.259	0.351	-0.161	0.237	0.280	0.329	0.310	0.320	0.317
Plant E1	0.298	-0.051	0.438	0.421	0.458	0.064	0.385	0.465	0.481	0.474	0.478	0.371
Plant modE1	0.282	0.021	0.345	0.322	0.377	-0.070	0.286	0.341	0.372	0.356	0.363	0.325
Plant E3	-0.144	0.075	-0.303	-0.309	-0.267	-0.182	-0.262	-0.350	-0.339	-0.349	-0.351	-0.187

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12. Supplementary Figures

Vegetation type	Vegetation classification
Mixed deciduous forests	Thermophilous mixed deciduous broadleaved forests, mainly hop-hornbeam (<i>Ostrya carpinifolia</i>) and oriental hornbeam (<i>Carpinus orientalis</i>) forests and colline oriental hornbeam-downy oak (<i>Quercus pubescens</i>) forests from the submediterranean belt
Maquis	Or garrigue in cases where vegetation is less than 1 m in height; degraded stages of sclerophyllous Mediterranean forests and scrub
Other shrublands	Mostly shibljak but also pseudomaquis (Čarni et al., 2018) from the meso- to oromediterranean treeless vegetation
Deciduous oak woodlands	Thermophilous mixed deciduous oak forests; mainly Hungarian oak forests (<i>Quercus frainetto</i>) and Macedonian oak forests (<i>Quercus trojana</i>)
Grasslands	Submediterranean / subcontinental to alpine treeless vegetation with dominance of herbs (steppe-like nutrient-poor (Pirini et al., 2014), and alpine grasslands)
Pine-dominated stands	Mediterranean black pine forests (<i>Pinus nigra</i>), Scots pine forests (<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>) and Balkan pine forests (<i>Pinus heldreichii</i>) from the supra- to submediterranean, from the oromediterranean, and from the altimediterranean vegetation belt, respectively
Beech-dominated stands	Moesian beech forests
Mixed fir forests	Fir forest (mainly without beech)

1045 **Supplementary Figure 1:** The eight vegetation types applied in this study and their correspondence with the vegetation
 1046 classifications in Barbati et al. (2007) and Bohn et al. (2000/2003) where appropriate.

1048 **Supplementary Figure 2:** Ordination diagram showing results of Detrended Correspondence Analysis (DCA) for the
 1049 datasets of plant (a-c) and pollen assemblages (d-f). The environmental variables (elevation (a, d), canopy cover (b, e), and
 1050 distance to the sea (c, f) were added passively and are shown as isolines. Their fit into the ordination is shown as r^2 .
 1051 Vegetation types have been represented as hulls in different colors (see legend at the bottom of the ordination plots). Three
 1052 asterisks (***) indicate $p < 0.001$.

Full pollen dataset

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Supplementary Figure 3: a) Pollen richness [PRI, orange] with Probability of Interspecific Encounter (PIE) evenness for pollen [purple] and b) detrended pollen richness [DE-PRI, red] for the full pollen dataset organised within same vegetation types along increasing elevation (as in Figure 1).

Pollen subset of wind-pollinated trees and shrubs

1058 **Supplementary Figure 4:** a) Pollen richness [PRI, orange] with Probability of Interspecific Encounter (PIE) evenness for
 1059 pollen [purple] and b) detrended pollen richness [DE-PRI, red] for the subset of wind-pollinated trees and shrubs organised
 1060 within same vegetation types along increasing elevation (as in Figure 1).

Plant subset of wind-pollinated trees and shrubs

1062 **Supplementary Figure 5:** Plant richness [N0, green] with Probability of Interspecific Encounter (PIE) evenness for plants
 1063 [darkblue] for the subset of wind-pollinated trees and shrubs organised within same vegetation types along increasing
 1064 elevation (as in Figure 1).
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13. Supplementary Datasets

1067 **Supplementary Dataset 1:** Raw plant records for each sampling site.

1068 Pub_plant_records_R.csv

1069 **Supplementary Dataset 1:** Plant attributes table with pollen equivalents, (MHVar.), (accVar.), growing form combined
1070 (Gfcomb), growing form (GF), and pollination mode (anemogam, zoogam, autogam, apogam) for each recorded plant
1071 species.

1072 Pub_plant_attributes_R.csv

1073 **Supplementary Dataset 3:** Plant records transformed into their pollen equivalents for each sampling site.

1074 Pub_pollen_equivalent_R.csv

1075 **Supplementary Dataset 42:** Raw pollen counts for each sampling site.

1076 Pub_pollen_records_R.csv

1077 **Supplementary Dataset 5:** Pollen attributes table with (MHVar.), (accVar.), growing form combined (Gfcomb), growing
1078 form (GF), and pollination mode (anemogam, zoogam, autogam, apogam) for each recorded pollen taxon.

1079 Pub_pollen_attributes_R.csv

1080 **Supplementary Dataset 6:** Raw pollen counts for the lake surface sediment samples (lake sediment surface samples (Limni
1081 Amvrakia (AMV), Limni Dojran (DOJ), Limni Ioannina (IOA), Limni Kastoria (KAS16), Limni Koroneia (KOR), Limni
1082 Petres (PET16), Limni Megali Prespa (PRE), Drakolimni Smolika (SMO), Limni Strofilia (STRO), Limni Vegoritis
1083 (VEG16), Limni Volvi (VOL), Limni Zazari (ZAZ16)).

1084 Pub_pollen_records_lakes_R.csv

1085 **Supplementary R-Code:** Diversity matrix for the pollen data set (N0 (equal to PRI), DE-PRI, N1, N2, PIE, N1-N2, N2/N1,
1086 N1/N0, modN2/modN1, modN1/modN0).

1087 Pub_pollen_diversity_matrix_R.R

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